

Neutron Activation Analysis of Sodium in Biological Samples Using Am-Be Source

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Sodium has been determined in 20 edible plant leaves and some beans by instrumental neutron activation analysis (INAA) using a low flux $^{241}\text{Am-Be}$ neutron source. The method involves irradiation for 24 hr followed by counting for 40 min on NaI(Tl) crystal detector and single channel analyzer. The amount of sodium varies from about 900 ppm to 3%. The method is simple, fast, non-destructive and reliable.

LOW flux portable neutron sources have been widely used for neutron activation analysis of several elements¹⁻⁴ in various matrices. The available thermal neutron flux of these sources is very low (10^5 - 10^6 n cm⁻² sec⁻¹) which restrict their use to the determination of only a few elements having high natural abundance and thermal neutron cross section alongwith preferably short lived resultant product nuclide⁵⁻⁷.

Sodium is one of the essential elements needed for various metabolic processes in human beings^{8,9}. Usually, it is consumed in the form of common salt but is also available in edible plant leaves which form a part of our daily diet. Therefore, knowledge of sodium content in plants is of great importance. Most chemical and instrumental methods, e.g., flame photometry, complex formation etc., available for the analysis of sodium are destructive in nature¹⁰. Neutron activation analysis (NAA) has been widely used for the multielemental analysis of biological samples¹¹⁻¹⁴ irradiated in a reactor. We have analyzed about 20 edible plant leaves and some beans for their sodium content by INAA. The principal nuclear reaction is $^{23}\text{Na}(n, \gamma)^{24}\text{Na}$, where the product nuclide decays by β -emission followed by γ -rays of 1.37 MeV and half life 15 hr. It is found that most plant leaves contain < 1% sodium. Replicate analyses have shown it to be a simple, fast and reliable method.

Experimental

Green leaf vegetables and beans were purchased from the local market. The excessive stems and roots were cut off and the leaves were thoroughly washed with water to remove any foreign material. These were then dried in the sun or in an oven at 90°. The dried samples were crushed to powder in a glass mortar and pestle and passed through plastic sieve to keep the particle size uniform. Standard Kale leaves powder¹⁵ was obtained from Professor Bowen and used as such.

The samples and the standard were dried in oven at 90° for 24 hr before packing for irradiation.

About 2 g dried sample was packed in snap top polythene vial. These were handled by wearing hand gloves or with forceps to avoid sodium contamination from sweat of hands.

The samples and the standard were irradiated for 24 hr simultaneously in a 5 Curie $^{241}\text{Am-Be}$ neutron cell (flux approximately 10^6 neutrons cm⁻² sec⁻¹) supplied by Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Bombay. A blank vial was also irradiated for background correction. The samples were cooled for 1 hr and activity due to 1.37 MeV photopeak from ^{24}Na was counted for 40 min on a well type $1.75'' \times 2''$ NaI(Tl) crystal and associated single channel gamma ray spectrometer supplied by ECIL, Hyderabad. Five sets of replicate analyses were performed for each sample.

Results and Discussion

The results of five replicate analyses of sodium in various vegetable leaves and beans (covers and seeds separately) are given in Table 1. Also given in the Table are mean values and standard deviations. These values were calculated assuming sodium content of Kale standard as 0.25%. Professor Bowen¹⁵ has given the best value in Kale as 2491 ± 379 ppm.

It is found that spinach leaves are most enriched with $3.02 \pm 0.39\%$ sodium, although purslane, goose-foot and sowa are the other leaves having more than 1% sodium. Spinach, orchard and tomato leaves and pine needles have been adopted as "Standard Reference Materials" (SRM) by National Bureau of Standards, USA but certified sodium content is not given for any of these samples. Therefore, a comparison of our values is not possible. However, Nadkarni¹¹ has analysed these NBS standards by reactor irradiation and given sodium content of $1.31 \pm 0.07\%$ for spinach, 522 ± 13 ppm for tomato leaves and 26 ± 4 ppm for pine needles. Our values for locally collected samples are $3.02 \pm 0.39\%$, 2060 ± 190 ppm and 2560 ± 50 ppm, respectively. Our results are high but within reasonable limits

TABLE 1—REPLICATE ANALYSIS OF BIOLOGICAL SAMPLES BY INAA

Sl. No.	Name (English/Local*)	Botanical name	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3	Run 4	Run 5	Mean with standard deviation
1.	Spinach/Palak	<i>Spinacea oleracea</i>	8.09	2.56	2.88	2.93	3.63	3.018 ± 0.392
2.	Purslane/Kulfa	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	1.50	2.12	2.38	1.94	1.89	1.967 ± 0.322
3.	Goosefoot/Chaulai	<i>Amaranthus chenopodian</i>	0.993	1.29	1.85	1.46	1.38	1.395 ± 0.311
4.	Sowa/Sepu	<i>Peucedanum graveolens</i>	0.741	0.981	0.728	1.06	1.10	0.921 ± 0.175
5.	Onion/Pyaz	<i>Allium cepa</i>	0.624	0.712	0.633	0.626	0.639	0.647 ± 0.026
6.	Fennugreek/Methi	<i>Trigonella foenumgraceum</i>	0.440	0.496	0.584	0.474	0.561	0.511 ± 0.060
7.	Betal leaves/Kapuri pan	<i>Piper betal</i>	0.454	0.556	0.466	0.478	0.874	0.506 ± 0.055
8.	Betal leaves/Bangla pan	<i>Piper betal</i>	0.234	0.264	0.267	0.202	0.356	0.245 ± 0.037
9.	Khatta palak	<i>Rumex vasicarius</i>	0.504	0.419	0.399	0.651	0.445	0.484 ± 0.102
10.	Cauliflower/Fulgobhi	<i>Brassica oleracea</i> Var. <i>capitata</i>	0.350	0.468	0.509	0.519	0.485	0.466 ± 0.058
11.	Coriander/Dhania patti	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	0.353	0.428	0.277	0.330	0.407	0.359 ± 0.060
12.	Radish/Mooli	<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	0.219	0.323	0.250	0.243	0.221	0.259 ± 0.045
13.	Pineapple/Ananas	<i>Ananas sativus</i>	0.261	0.261	0.254	0.248	—	0.256 ± 0.005
14.	Tomato leaves	<i>Lycopersicon esculantum</i>	0.231	0.218	0.194	0.201	0.186	0.206 ± 0.019
15.	Cabbage/Pattagobhi	<i>Brassica oleracea</i> Var. <i>botrytis</i>	0.181	0.295	0.152	0.216	0.192	0.183 ± 0.024
16.	Lalbhaji	<i>Amaranthus gangeticus</i>	0.176	0.176	0.194	0.200	0.158	0.181 ± 0.016
17.	Curry leaf/Meetha neem	<i>Murraya koenigii</i>	0.227	0.167	0.173	0.154	0.171	0.178 ± 0.028
18.	Mint/Podina	<i>Mentha piperata</i>	0.171	0.168	0.175	0.175	0.189	0.176 ± 0.009
19.	Grape leaves/Angur	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	0.089	0.092	0.091	0.104	0.089	0.093 ± 0.006
20.	Country bean (covers)/Sem	<i>Dolichos lablab</i>	0.196	0.107	0.138	0.128	0.121	0.138 ± 0.024
21.	Country bean (seeds)/Sem	—do—	0.181	0.100	0.119	0.104	0.113	0.111 ± 0.008
22.	Chaulai bean (covers)	<i>Vigna catjang</i>	0.195	0.143	0.208	0.123	0.180	0.170 ± 0.036
23.	Chaulai bean (seeds)	—do—	0.120	0.054	0.120	0.116	0.099	0.102 ± 0.029
24.	Pea/Muttor (covers)	<i>Pisum sativum</i>			Not detectable			
25.	Pea/Muttor (seeds)	—do—			—do—			

* Local name refers to that in Hindi or Marathi.

except the one for pine needles. We also analyzed NBS standard spinach-SRM 1570 but its sodium content was found to be $0.75 \pm 0.045\%$ only. We chose Kale as a standard rather than spinach (SRM 1570) because it has been widely analyzed. It is quite possible that our locally collected species may be different from those adopted by NBS as standards. We also tried to check our results on standard Kale assuming anhydrous sodium acetate as standard but this being of different matrix does not compare well. In order to check purity, we also followed the half lives for some samples. Half life determination of sodium in spinach, purslane, sowa and goosefoot samples gave a value of 15.0 hr which is in good agreement with literature¹⁶ value.

We have also analyzed some beans like country beans, chaulai beans and peas for their sodium content in covers and seeds separately. It is found that for country beans and chaulai beans, the covers are more enriched in sodium than the seeds. However, for peas, sodium could not be detected in either cover or seeds. Presumably sodium content is much below 1000 ppm which is the detectable limit for our experimental set up. It has been pointed out by several workers^{14,17} that plants may take up some elements from soil in a preferential manner so as to accumulate them in a particular part of the plant. In the present investigation it seems that sodium is accumulated more in the covers of the beans than in the seeds but overall sodium is more in leaves. Presumably, seeds being rich in proteins have less affinity for sodium and comparatively more sodium gets accumulated in the bean covers than in the

seeds. Further, comparatively more sodium is accumulated in leaves of the plant than in the seeds or pod covers.

Interestingly, two types of betal leaves, *Kapuri* and *Bangla*, differ in their sodium content (0.506 and 0.24%, respectively) by a factor of two. Mint and coriander leaves are also consumed in large amounts as seasoning to cooked vegetables but their sodium contents are only 0.176 and 0.359%, respectively.

A cursory look at the Table indicates that in some cases there are large variations in individual analyses in columns 1 to 5. This is reflected in standard deviation also which is approximately 10-30% of the mean value. Therefore, the method is good only to have an estimate of relative amounts of sodium by non-destructive method. However, it has definite advantages over the conventional methods of sodium determination. For a large number of samples it is quite economic and fast. The method works well for sodium content of 1000 ppm or more and a sample size of about 2 g but precision decreases for smaller amounts.

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